

THE IMPACT OF MUSCULAR STRENGTH ON THE SIT-TO-STAND TASK IN INDIVIDUALS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Abstract. Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological condition characterized by the degeneration of dopaminergic cells in the substantia nigra [1]. Individuals with PD experience a range of motor and nonmotor symptoms throughout the progression of the disease. While bradykinesia, muscle rigidity, and tremors are commonly recognized motor symptoms, patients often report difficulties in activities such as rising from a chair or performing the sit-to-stand (STS) task [2]. The STS task holds significant importance in overall mobility, determining functional independence, and influencing the quality of life [2, 3]. It is estimated that approximately 44% of PD patients encounter some level of difficulty in performing this task [2].

Various abnormalities in kinematics, joint torques, and postural stability are considered crucial in understanding the abnormal STS task observed in PD patients [4–6]. Lower limb muscle weakness is frequently reported by PD patients, with many attributing their challenges in rising from a chair to this perceived weakness [7, 8]. Clinicians often encounter a clinical paradox where neurological examinations reveal normal muscle strength in the lower limbs of PD patients, despite notable abnormalities in the STS task that are sometimes linked to weakness.

Several studies have demonstrated decreased muscle strength in PD patients using reliable, quantitative methods [9–11]. These findings include reports of reduced lower limb muscle strength, particularly at the hip level, associated with difficulties in the STS task [5, 12]. Conversely, some studies have not identified differences in muscle strength during the STS task between PD patients and healthy controls [13]. However, the limited sample sizes in these studies prompted our investigation, where we assessed muscle strength in PD patients and matched healthy controls using clinical and dynamometric methods and correlated the findings with the STS task in these individuals.

Objective: Our goal is to ascertain the influence of muscle strength on the sit-to-stand (STS) task.

Keywords: Dopaminergic cells, substantia nigra, bradykinesia, tremor, neurological abnormalities.

Materials and methods:

We recruited consecutive patients diagnosed with Parkinson's disease (PD) from a tertiary-care center specializing in movement disorders. Inclusion criteria comprised individuals of both genders, aged 18 years or older, with a confirmed diagnosis of Parkinson's disease according to the Queen Square Brain Bank Criteria [14]. Exclusion criteria excluded patients with Parkinsonism not meeting PD diagnostic criteria and those with musculoskeletal or neurological abnormalities that could independently lead to lower limb motor strength reduction, irrespective of PD.

Clinical assessments were conducted using the Movement Disorders Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale part III or motor score (MDS-UPDRS-III). Signs of severe

neuropathy and spasticity, including abnormal muscle reflexes and the Babinski sign, were examined in all patients. Item 3.9 "arising from chair" from the MDS-UPDRS-III was employed to evaluate the sit-to-stand (STS) task, with scores categorized into sublevels ranging from 0 to 4. For this study, we defined an "abnormal" score as equal to or higher than 2. Composite scores for leg tremor, rigidity, and bradykinesia were calculated.

Disease stage was determined using the modified Hoehn and Yahr scale [15], and the total levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD) was assessed [16]. Dyskinesia presence, orthostatic hypotension (OH), and its definition were recorded during the neurological examination. We also assessed the frequency of perceived lower limb weakness in patients and controls, considering abnormal lower limb sensations within the spectrum of weakness. The functional impact of weakness was rated as "mild," "moderate," or "severe." Additionally, 52 sex- and age-matched healthy controls were enrolled, with lower limb strength, perceived weakness, and associated sensations assessed.

Manual muscle testing, utilizing the Medical Research Council (MRC) Scale [18], and dynamometric calculations (ZP-500, Digital Force Gauge, Alipo, China) were employed to assess the strengths of the iliopsoas, rectus femoris, sartorius, and pectineus muscles. The rectus femoris, vastus lateralis, vastus medialis, vastus intermedius, hamstrings (biceps femoris, semitendinosus, and semimembranosus), gracilis, sartorius, gastrocnemius, and popliteus muscles were individually evaluated in each leg during sequential leg pressure on the floor using a calibrated weighing machine.

Results:

We examined 15 consecutive patients diagnosed with Parkinson's disease (PD). Two patients were excluded – one with lumbar stenosis leading to lower limb weakness and another with an initial presentation of Parkinsonism due to a glioma. Our analysis focused on the remaining 13 PD patients. Among them, 3 (26.3%) exhibited an abnormal sit-to-stand (STS) task, as indicated by a score of ≥ 2 points on item 3.9. There were no discernible differences in age and sex distribution between PD patients with and without abnormal STS tasks. The duration of PD progression did not show variance between the two groups.

However, patients with an abnormal STS task displayed a higher modified Hoehn and Yahr (HY) stage, a higher total score on the Movement Disorders Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale part III (MDS-UPDRS-III), and were taking higher doses of levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD), although this last variable did not reach statistical significance ($P = 0.174$) (see Table 1). No notable difference in orthostatic hypotension (OH) was observed between the groups. A greater proportion of patients with abnormal STS tasks reported perceived lower limb weakness and associated sensations ($P = 0.004$) compared to those with normal STS tasks, and they rated these abnormal sensations more severely (see Table 1). The presence of perceived lower limb weakness significantly increased the risk of having an abnormal STS task, with an odds ratio (OR) of 11.93 (95% confidence interval: 1.51–94.32).

Discussion

In our investigation, we observed that individuals with Parkinson's disease (PD) exhibiting moderate-to-severe abnormalities in the sit-to-stand (STS) task (≥ 2 points in item 3.9 of the MDS-UPDRS-III) reported heightened concerns related to lower limb weakness and perceived this weakness as more severe when compared to PD patients with a normal STS task. The

presence of perceived lower limb weakness was identified as a significant factor, elevating the risk of an abnormal STS task by 11.93.

Furthermore, those with PD and moderate-to-severe abnormalities in the STS task displayed elevated scores in the Hoehn and Yahr scale and MDS-UPDRS part III. This suggests that central motor abnormalities, particularly lower limb bradykinesia and rigidity, might contribute to the challenges faced in rising from a chair. These individuals exhibited reduced muscle strength in the lower extremities compared to PD patients with a normal STS task and the control group. Notably, the assessment of isokinetic muscle contractions at the hip level revealed weakened torque at the coxofemoral joint, suggesting a potential influence on the dynamics of the STS task. We found that diminished muscle torque during hip extension (≤ 9 kg) significantly increased the risk of an abnormal STS task. However, this distinction was not observed in hip flexion as assessed by dynamometric measures.

The relatively marginal disparity in muscle strength between PD patients with a normal or abnormal STS task, as well as normal controls, implies that reduced muscle strength only partially accounts for the difficulties observed in the STS task among most PD patients. Moreover, these limitations in muscle strength may be challenging to identify in routine clinical examinations.

Conclusion:

Irregularities in the Sit-to-Stand (STS) task play a crucial role in the mobility of individuals with Parkinson's disease (PD). The underlying causes of these abnormalities are not fully comprehended, but they appear to involve dynamic muscle adjustments aimed at controlling the displacement of the Center of Mass (COM) and ensuring the proper transmission of torque to the joints in the lower extremities. Patients experiencing difficulties in the STS task often report lower limb weakness, related sensations, and a reduction in muscle strength, particularly in the hip region. An independent association was observed between an abnormal STS task and muscle strength measuring ≤ 9 kg for hip extension and leg bradykinesia. This implies the involvement of both peripheral and central mechanisms in the abnormal rising from a chair among PD patients.

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